

Study on ^{11}B -NMR of Borates in their Saturated Aqueous Solutions

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The ^{11}B nuclear magnetic resonance studies of six series of borates in their saturated aqueous solutions have been done and their ^{11}B -nmr chemical shifts have been given. The saturated solutions of borates containing $\text{B}_2\text{O}_4^{2-}$, $\text{B}_4\text{O}_7^{2-}$, $\text{B}_6\text{O}_{10}^{2-}$ and BO_4^{1-} units yield separately almost only one-line spectra that their chemical shift of ^{11}B -nmr appearing at the same position and the borates containing B_5O_8^- unit, three main peaks. The forms of polymerised borate ions existing in solution might be deduced.

In the recent years, the ^{11}B mass nmr of borates have been widely studied and the mass structures of the borates have been determined by X-ray diffraction, ir and Raman spectra and other modern physical methods. However, the solution structures of polyborate anions have not been systematically studied because of their multiplicity and complexity, so only several ordinary borate species such as borax, potassium pentaborate solutions have been investigated, and some of the polyborate anion forms existing in solution have been suggested. It is very important and necessary to measure ^{11}B nmr spectra of those solutions in different concentrations. On account of the polymerization and depolymerization of borate anions in different concentrations, the more and more weaker ^{11}B signal at lower concentrations makes the work difficult and tedious to perform. Fortunately, the development of high-performance nmr instrument provides the possibility to probe the solution structure of borates. We have studied six series of borate samples at their saturated aqueous solutions and some new results have been obtained.

Results and Discussion

Here, 12 saturated borate solutions have been studied. Among them, the ^{11}B nmr chemical shifts of borax, potassium pentaborate, potassium tetraborate and sodium pentaborate solutions somewhat differ from that reported in literatures^{1,2} and the ^{11}B nmr chemical shifts of the solutions of other samples are reported for the first time. The results are presented in Table 1.

$\text{B}_4\text{O}_7^{2-}$ (may be expressed as $\text{B}_4\text{O}_5(\text{OH})_2^{2-}$) series: The ^{11}B nmr of saturated solutions of $\text{MgB}_4\text{O}_7 \cdot 9\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (~11.8 ppm), $\text{Li}_2\text{B}_4\text{O}_7 \cdot 3\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (~10.1 ppm), $\text{Na}_2\text{B}_4\text{O}_7 \cdot 10\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (~9.2 ppm) and $\text{K}_2\text{B}_4\text{O}_7 \cdot 4\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (~9.3 ppm) (0.86), ~1.4 ppm (0.14) have been determined under the same condition. The results show that the chemical sites of ^{11}B in different saturated solutions do not change very much and this is just as the case of ^{11}B nuclear in the diluting processes of borax saturated solution under the same temperature. It is reasonable to think that the cations Li^+ , Na^+ , K^+ and Mg^{2+} have almost no effect on the anion $\text{B}_4\text{O}_5(\text{OH})_2^{2-}$ or its

depolymerized anions [perhaps $\text{B}_3\text{O}_3(\text{OH})_4^-$, $\text{B}(\text{OH})_4^-$, $\text{B}_2\text{O}(\text{OH})_4^-$, $\text{B}_2\text{O}(\text{OH})_6^{2-}$ etc.] of its higher polymerised anions [may be $\text{B}_5\text{O}_6(\text{OH})_4^{1-}$]^{1,3}. The cations do not directly change the chemical surroundings of boron atoms in solutions but modify the solubilities of the metal tetraborates, so the total boron concentration in the solution is different and the existing forms of boron verified. The recorded ^{11}B nmr peaks, which concern with the boron forms in the solutions, are found shifted.

TABLE I—CHEMICAL SHIFTS OF ^{11}B NMR IN DIFFERENT SATURATED BORATE SOLUTIONS AT 298 K

Borates	Anions	^{11}B chem. shift (ppm) (relative intensity)
$\text{CaB}_2\text{O}_4 \cdot 4\text{H}_2\text{O}^*$	$\text{B}_2\text{O}_4^{2-}$	3.06
$\text{Ca}_2\text{B}_6\text{O}_{11} \cdot 9\text{H}_2\text{O}^*$	$\text{B}_6\text{O}_{11}^{4-}$	8.02
$\text{Mg}_2\text{B}_6\text{O}_{11} \cdot 17\text{H}_2\text{O}^*$	$\text{B}_6\text{O}_{11}^{4-}$	7.51
$\text{Li}_2\text{B}_4\text{O}_7 \cdot 3\text{H}_2\text{O}$	$\text{B}_4\text{O}_7^{2-}$	10.05
$\text{Na}_2\text{B}_4\text{O}_7 \cdot 10\text{H}_2\text{O}$	$\text{B}_4\text{O}_7^{2-}$	9.27 8.7 ^a
$\text{K}_2\text{B}_4\text{O}_7 \cdot 4\text{H}_2\text{O}$	$\text{B}_4\text{O}_7^{2-}$	1.37 (0.14), 9.35 (0.86). 0.9 (0.02), 7.6 (0.98), 11.6 ^a (0.40 M)
$\text{MgB}_4\text{O}_7 \cdot 9\text{H}_2\text{O}^*$	$\text{B}_4\text{O}_7^{2-}$	11.80
$\text{LiB}_5\text{O}_8 \cdot 5\text{H}_2\text{O}$	B_5O_8^-	1.19 (0.17), 13.32 (0.39), 18.71 (0.43)
$\text{NaB}_5\text{O}_8 \cdot 5\text{H}_2\text{O}$	B_5O_8^-	1.27 (0.13), 13.15 (0.34), 18.60 (0.54), 1.0 (0.16), 13.2 (0.25), 18.9 (0.59) ^b , (0.40 M)
$\text{KB}_5\text{O}_8 \cdot 4\text{H}_2\text{O}$	B_5O_8^-	1.34 (0.10), 13.33 (0.29), 18.08 (0.56), 27.28 (0.05), 0.9 (0.048), 12.8 (0.348), 17.9 (0.604) ^b , (0.15 M), 0.9, 13.0, 17.7 ^b (314 K. saturated solution)
$\text{CaB}_6\text{O}_{10} \cdot 4\text{H}_2\text{O}^*$	$\text{B}_6\text{O}_{10}^{2-}$	14.48, 29.95 (very weak)
$\text{MgB}_6\text{O}_{10} \cdot 7\text{H}_2\text{O}^*$	$\text{B}_6\text{O}_{10}^{2-}$	14.57

* ^{11}B nmr chemical shifts reported for the first time

^aRef. 2, ^bRef. 1.

The $\text{K}_2\text{B}_4\text{O}_7 \cdot 4\text{H}_2\text{O}$ saturated solution, however, yields two line spectra, this might be explained as that $\text{K}_2\text{B}_4\text{O}_7 \cdot 4\text{H}_2\text{O}$ has a relative large solubility in water and as a dynamic equilibrium, the B_5O_8^- (may be expressed as

$B_5O_6(OH)_4^-$ was formed in the solution and the 1.37 (0.14) ppm peak might be assigned to it.

$B_5O_8^-$ (may be expressed as $B_5O_6(OH)_4^-$) series : The number and positions of ^{11}B nmr peaks might be changed in different concentrated solutions of the different pentaborates but three main peaks (~18, ~13 and ~1 ppm) are always observed at almost the same positions. This result supports previous works^{1,3} that the assignments of the resonance belong to $B(OH)_3/B(OH)_4^-$, $B_3O_3(OH)_4^-$ and $B_5O_6(OH)_4^-$ respectively. Salentine¹ reported the same result and regarded that the resonance at 1 ppm is due to the $B_5O_6(OH)_4^-$ anion and the other two resonances arise from the rapid exchanges among boron sites in different polymerized borates anions. However, the recent ^{11}B mass nmr studies⁴ suggest that the B[3] : B[4] = 80 : 20 in solid $KB_5O_8 \cdot 4H_2O$ could be written as $K[B_5O_6(OH)_4 \cdot 2H_2O]$, so the structure of $B_5O_6(OH)_4^-$ anion might be expressed as follows⁵ :

It is shown that there are two different chemical and nmr sites on ^{11}B in this anion, then two nmr peaks should be observed. This will just defy the former results and it is reasonable to consider that the following reactions might exist in the solution :

These reactions have been assumed by Ingri⁶ and supported by the temperature-jump studies of Anderson and Eyring⁷. Moreover, diluting experiments show that the ^{11}B nmr peak of H_3BO_3 do not change its position with the boron concentrations and always appears at ~19.6 ppm at the same temperature. So we have some evidences to postulate that the ~18 ppm peak comes from the B[3] atom in $B_5O_6(OH)_4^-$ anion, the ~13 ppm peak could be regarded as a rapid exchange process between $B_3O_3(OH)_4^-$ and the B[3] atoms in $B_5O_6(OH)_4^-$, and the ~1 ppm peak as the centre boron atom $B_5O_6(OH)_4^-$ respectively. Furthermore, a lower field peak appeared at the ^{11}B nmr spectroscopy of concentrated $KB_5O_8 \cdot 4H_2O$ solution at about 27.3 ppm. Be-

cause this peak is very weak (~0.05), we might regard it as the 'naked' peak of the centre boron in $B_5O_6(OH)_4^-$ anion with the further diluting and formed hydrated anion.

$CaB_2O_4 \cdot 4H_2O$: The chemical shift of ^{11}B in the saturated solution is 3.06 ppm. According to former works, the chemical shift of ^{11}B in $B(OH)_4^-$ is about 3.34 ppm, so the chemical shift of ^{11}B in diluted $CaB_2O_4 \cdot 4H_2O$ solution would also be near 3.34 ppm because of the following reactions :

However, in $CaB_2O_4 \cdot 4H_2O$ saturated solution, the dissociation of $B_2O_2(OH)_4^{2-}$ is not complete, the measured ^{11}B chemical shift is a 'synthetical' one of $B_2O_2(OH)_4^{2-}$ and $B(OH)_4^-$ so the dissociation constant of $B_2O_2(OH)_4^{2-}$ at the experimental condition could be roughly calculated².

$B_6O_7^-$ series : The crystal structure analysis shows that the $B_3O_3(OH)_3^{2-}$ group exists in $Ca_2B_6O_{11} \cdot 9H_2O$ crystal and the $B_3O_3(OH)_3^{3-}$ group is contained in $MgB_6O_{11} \cdot 17H_2O$ crystal⁵. The difference of the existing form of the hydrated $B_6O_7^-$ anion is mainly due to the difference of the number of hydrated water of cations (Ca^{2+} and Mg^{2+}). However, when these compounds are dissolved into water and become saturated solutions, the polymerized anions in the crystals might be changed. Then it is reasonable to think that the $B_3O_3(OH)_3^{2-}$ and $B_3O_3(OH)_3^{3-}$ are the most important polyborate anions in the solutions and the following reaction might have occurred :

Then the main anions existing in $Ca_2B_6O_{11} \cdot 9H_2O$ and $MgB_6O_{11} \cdot 17H_2O$ solutions are almost the same and the ^{11}B nmr peaks of the two solutions appear at almost the same position. Furthermore, the enhancement of electron clouds density around the boron atoms changed the position of ^{11}B nmr peak from ~13 ppm of $B_3O_3(OH)_4^-$ to ~8 ppm ($Ca_2B_6O_{11} \cdot 9H_2O$: ~8.0 ppm; $MgB_6O_{11} \cdot 17H_2O$: ~7.5 ppm) of $B_3O_3(OH)_3^{2-}/B_3O_3(OH)_3^{3-}$.

$B_6O_7^-$ series : Although the crystal structures of $CaB_6O_{10} \cdot 4H_2O$ and $MgB_6O_{10} \cdot 7H_2O$ are different⁵, the results of ^{11}B nmr studies show that their solution structures are very similar (~14.5 ppm ~ 14.6 ppm of boron-11 chemical shift). That is to say that $B_6O_7(OH)_6^{2-}$ (existed in $CaB_6O_{10} \cdot 4H_2O$ crystals) and the $B_6O_9(OH)_2^{2-}$ (existed in $MgB_6O_{10} \cdot 7H_2O$ crystals) have concordant structural forms

in their saturated solutions. According to their crystal structure and boron-11 nmr properties, the following structures could be suggested as the structural form of $\text{B}_6\text{O}_7(\text{OH})_6^{2-}$ and $\text{B}_6\text{O}_9(\text{OH})_2^{2-}$ in saturated solutions :

The fast exchange of OH^- between different boron atom in solution makes it difficult to extinguish different boron atoms, and the three hexagonal structural form of B-O bond induced the similarity of the above mentioned structural formulas in solutions. So the chemical shift of ^{11}B atom in the solutions of $\text{CaB}_6\text{O}_{10}\cdot 4\text{H}_2\text{O}$ and $\text{MgB}_6\text{O}_{10}\cdot 7\text{H}_2\text{O}$ appeared at almost the same position.

Experimental

Nmr spectra were obtained on an Unity 200 (Valian Co., USA) 200 MHz spectrometer (corresponding to a ^{11}B nmr frequency of 64.18 MHz). The solution 90° pulse width for boron trifluoride etherate ($\text{BF}_3\cdot\text{Et}_2\text{O}$) was 6.75 μs

and Acq., time, 1.49 s. Chemical shifts are reported in ppm from an external sample of $\text{BF}_3\cdot\text{Et}_2\text{O}$ and positive values correspond to low-field, high-frequency. The decouple pulse width was 17.50 μs of ^1H at 8840.00 Hz. All the experiments were operated under constant temperature at 298 K.

The saturated borate solutions were prepared with analytical pure reagent. The purity of synthesised products prepare in our laboratory, was checked by physical and chemical methods such as chemical analysis, X-ray diffraction, ir and Raman spectra⁸ and then dissolved into redistilled water at room temperature. The chemical shift of ^{11}B nmr in boric acid (Merck, G.R.) solution was used as a standard reference.

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References

1. C. G. SALENTINE, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1983, **22**, 3920.
2. R. K. MOMII and N. H. NACHTRIEB, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1967, **6**, 1189.
3. H. D. SMITH, JR. and R. J. WIERSEMA, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1972, **11**, 1152.
4. D. MÜLLER und A.R. GRIMMER, U. TIMPEF, G. HELLER und M. SHAKIBAIE-MOGHAHAM, *Z. Anorg. Allg. Chem.*, 1993, **619**, 1262.
5. G. HELLER, *Top. Curr. Chem.*, 1986, **131**, 39.
6. N. INGRI, *Sven. Kem. Tidskr.*, 1963, **75**, 199.
7. J. L. ANDERSON and E. M. ERYING, *J. Phy. Chem.*, 1964, **68**, 1128.
8. LI JUN, XIA SHUPING and GAO SHIYANG, *Spectrochim Acta, Part A*, 1995, **51**, 519.